

**PREVENTING RADICALISATION AMONG YOUNG
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ARTICLE INFOReceived: 24th January 2026Accepted: 25th January 2026Online: 26th January 2026**KEYWORDS***terrorism, extremism, radicalism
prevention, security legislation***ABSTRACT***This article reflects the essence of the concept of
radicalisation and the main directions aimed at preventing
it.*

Over the centuries, religion has been an important factor in preserving and nurturing national culture, values, customs, and traditions, and has contributed to the advancement of spirituality.

Even today, religion continues to demonstrate its power to strongly influence personal development and societal progress.

Nevertheless, it is regrettable to note that the misuse of religion for malicious purposes, the propagation of extremist ideas under the guise of religion, and the perpetration of terrorist acts continue.

The harmony of social and spiritual life, national and democratic development is directly linked to the moral character, mindset, and the skills and knowledge of the younger generation in acquiring national, religious, and universal values. Indeed, studying religion impartially and scientifically, and examining it as a holistic social phenomenon, allows one to analyse its current state and religious issues systematically and determine its future prospects.

In our country, in the context of multi-confessionalism, ensuring harmony among representatives of various nations, ethnic groups, and religions, and making a worthy contribution to strengthening peace and stability in the world is considered a sacred duty of every citizen, especially of government officials. Strengthening interethnic and interfaith harmony on a global scale largely depends on the effective implementation of the principles of tolerance in social life.

As emphasized by our country's leader Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "the work aimed at strengthening the environment of interethnic harmony and tolerance in society is considered a priority direction in the domestic and foreign policy of our republic, bringing it to a qualitatively new level."

In this regard, taking into account the vital necessity arising from the evolutionary development of society, the new edition of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan

was adopted by a vote in the referendum held on 30 April 2023, with 90.21 percent of the citizens participating in the referendum voting in favor.

In the new edition of the Constitution, the number of articles increased from the current 128 to 155, and the number of provisions rose from 275 to 434. That is, the text of our Fundamental Law increased by almost 65 percent and was supplemented with new provisions based on the suggestions of our people.

Article 1 of the Constitution firmly establishes that "Uzbekistan is a sovereign, democratic, legal, social and secular state with a republican form of government".

In this topic, the principle of a secular state mentioned above will be discussed in detail, including its fundamental essence, the boundary between secularism and religion, as well as the fact that secularism does not reject religion.

A secular state is one in which freedom of conscience is guaranteed for everyone, separated from religious-confessional views and institutions, and governs in accordance with the Constitution and laws, based on the interests of society as a whole, in regulating social relations, making decisions, and implementing them.

Legislation, fair justice, and the formation and functioning of state authorities are carried out based on the principle of secularity. Regardless of the government's stance on religion, decisions are made for the entire society taking into account the interests of all citizens.

The state provides citizens with equal guarantees in exercising freedom of conscience and does not affiliate itself with any religion. Therefore, genuine religious freedoms can only be ensured in a secular state.

Although religion is separated from the state and politics in a secular state, it is not separated from society, but rather it is considered a factor in humans achieving spiritual and moral development.

Most importantly, a secular state aims not only to create equal conditions for all religions but also to provide citizens with the opportunity to pursue education, choose their personal development path independently, and ensure creative freedom in science and cultural progress.

In general, the state in a secular country remains officially neutral on religious matters or refrains from interfering in religious issues. One of the key features of a secular state is that representatives of different religions live in an atmosphere of tolerance and peace.

In a society where there are representatives of various religions, nations, ethnic groups, and cultures, state governance and politics cannot be based solely on a single ideology or religious view. In such conditions, the most just and right path for every country is the path of a secular state.

Designating Uzbekistan as a secular state serves global development, strengthens tolerance and harmony among representatives of different religions, allows religious organisations to operate independently, and ensures freedom of religion and belief.

In our multi-ethnic country, special attention is being paid to creating an atmosphere of mutual friendship and establishing the principles of tolerance among representatives of different faiths. In our country, more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups live together in

harmony and friendship, and over 2,300 religious organizations of 16 confessions carry out their activities.

The ongoing reforms are being appropriately recognised worldwide and are evaluated as a model of religious tolerance. In particular, Uzbekistan's removal from the list of countries of special concern in the field of religious freedom and the adoption of the “Education and Religious Tolerance” resolution proposed by Uzbekistan at the UN General Assembly session are clear examples of this.

Religiosity, fanaticism, extremism and terrorism are social phenomena formed by a person's relationship with religion, and they have a dynamic nature, meaning that they can either demand or contradict each other depending on time and place. It should be noted that these phenomena occur not only in Islam, but also in other world, national, or ethnoconfessional religions.

It is known that various factors influence the formation of religious belief in humans and the level of their piety. Although the emergence of religious views initially begins in the family, in later stages the range of factors affecting their development expands.

It should be noted that in psychology, the development of the human psyche is symbolically depicted using a pyramid shape. In this context, when illustrating the stages from a person's level of religiosity to becoming a terrorist, in our opinion, it should be depicted from the top down.

Because, even from a spiritual point of view, the formation of a terrorist individual is not a progressive but rather a regressive process and goes through several stages until reaching the lowest level, that is, depravity.

It is appropriate to mention several concepts when assessing the religious situation. Specifically, concepts such as religious neutrality, religiosity, intolerance, extremism, and terrorism exist, and the improvement of the religious situation is carried out by providing educational influence to intolerant individuals at the initial stages and thereby preventing them from progressing to the next stage. Therefore, based on the approach under the idea of Enlightenment against Ignorance, it is considered necessary to identify citizens who have gone astray in the religious path at the initial stage and to carry out purely ideological explanatory work with them.

At the same time, if most of these signs are observed, it is necessary to have an open and sincere conversation with this person with their parents, local community, educational institution or workplace system, to clarify the issues that caused this situation, and also to explain the threats and terrible consequences of radicalism and extremism ideology. In necessary cases, it is considered appropriate to consult specialists such as a scholar of Islam, a theologian, psychologist, or lawyer.

In this regard, young people need to pay attention to certain things to avoid falling under the influence of radical movements:

- Deeply mastering secular knowledge, forming an understanding of the role of religion in a secular state based on current legislation, and increasing political and legal literacy;

- According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is a secular state, guarantees freedom of conscience for everyone, ensures the right of everyone to practice any

religion or not to adhere to any religion at all, and firmly upholds that there should be no forced imposition of religious views.

- It is deeply understood that under the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is prohibited to use religion for the purpose of forcibly changing the constitutional order, undermining its sovereignty and territorial integrity, infringing on citizens' constitutional rights and freedoms, promoting religious hostility, disrupting citizens' harmony, as well as committing other actions directed against the individual, society and the state, and that punishment for crimes in this area is inevitable.

- To have independent thinking, a worldview formed on a sound basis and strong will, to deeply study and practice national and universal values.

- To treat other religions and cultures with respect and tolerance, not to consider one's own religion superior to others;

Use of officially permitted sources, familiarizing oneself with the list of materials considered extremist and terrorist by the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the import, preparation, distribution and demonstration of which are prohibited in the territory of Uzbekistan

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